

SPIRITUAL INTELLIGENCE OF SECONDARY LEVEL STUDENTS STUDYING IN MODERN AND INDIGENOUS SCHOOLS

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Abstract

This study was carried out to compare the Spiritual Intelligence of secondary level students studying in Modern and Indigenous Schools. Sample comprised of 600 secondary level students. Spiritual Intelligence Scale developed by Researcher (self-constructed) was employed for data collection. Statistical techniques employed were: Mean, Standard Deviation and Critical Ratio. Results revealed the significant difference between secondary level students of Modern and Indigenous schools in terms of Spiritual Intelligence.

Keywords: *Spiritual Intelligence, Modern and Indigenous schools.*

Introduction

Spiritual Intelligence is an Intelligence of a person by which he / she can evaluate the deeper meanings of goodness, the purpose of life, and the highest motivation of life. Spiritual Intelligence is “*the ability to behave with wisdom and compassion, while maintaining inner and outer peace, regardless of the situations*” (Wiggle worth et al., 2012). King (2005) described differences between religiosity and Spirituality “*Religiousness refers to set of social private (includes rituals) behaviors and attitudes which are based on the previous religious doctrine and institutional aliased organizations while Spirituality refers to set off unbounded behaviors, experience and attitudes which are based on existential understanding, meaning and purpose.*” Emotional Intelligence is the ability to perceive owns and other’s emotions to live a successful life. Emotional Intelligence includes awareness of self-regulation and desirable behavior or expression of a range of effective emotions. It is also the ability to handle their own emotions effectively and the ability to understand and manage the

relationship with others.

A person high in SQ doesn't need to have any religious faith or belief. However, a person low in S.Q. may have faith or belief in religious affairs and with spiritual intelligence, a person can evaluate good or bad things very efficiently. On the other hand, *“Spiritual intelligence is the ultimate intelligence by which we address and solve problems, meaning and value the intelligence through which we can place our actions and our lives, in a wide richer meaning, giving context to the intelligence with which we can assess that one's course of action or one's life path is more meaningful than the others”* (Zohar and Marshall, 2000).

Definition of the terms used

- **Spiritual Intelligence (S.I)** - is the ability to perceive emotions, to access and generate emotions so as to assist thought, to understand emotions and emotional knowledge and to reflectively regulate emotions so as to promote emotional and intellectual growth.
- **Modern schools** - Schools using modern teaching methods, content, and subjects are known as modern schools. They do not have a learning environment like indigenous schools and they give more priority to scientific and technical subjects or knowledge, they do not give much emphasis on metaphysics and philosophical subjects.
- **Indigenous schools** - Special focuses on teaching indigenous knowledge, models, method and content with in formal and non-formal education system.
- **Secondary school students** - Students studying in class 11 &12 included in the secondary school students.

Objective of the study

- To compare the Spiritual Intelligence of secondary level students studying in Modern and Indigenous Schools.

Hypothesis of the study

There exists no significant difference between Spiritual Intelligence of secondary level students studying in Modern and Indigenous schools.

Variables of the study

The variables of study were as follows:

Independent Variable: Indigenous schools & Modern schools

Dependent Variable: Spiritual Intelligence

Sample of the study:

This study was carried out on senior secondary students of Modern and Indigenous schools. Purposive method was employed for school selection whereas, Random sampling was used for unit selection. Sample comprised of total six hundred students.

Sampling Procedure of the Study:**Phase I: Selection of Schools**

In the present study, Modern and Indigenous schools have been selected by adopting the Purposive Method of sample selection.

Table 1: Distribution of Students in Modern and Indigenous Schools

Types of school		No. of Schools	Total Strength of Secondary Students		
			Male	Female	Total
Modern schools	U.P Board schools	02	140	120	260
	CBSE schools	02	95	79	174
Indigenous schools	Gurukula	02	85	80	165
	Madarsa	03	90	76	166
TOTAL		09	410	355	765

Thus, 765 students were available in Modern and Indigenous schools. Out of which only 600 students were available for the sample.

Phase-2: Selection of Sample

The Simple Random sampling method was used to collect the sample in present study. The sample was selected from various Modern (U.P. Board, CBSE Board) and Indigenous (Gurukula, Madrasa) secondary schools. In the present study, the sample consisted of 300 students (150 male & 150 female) from Modern schools and 300 students (150 male and 150 female) from Indigenous schools and the total sample included 600 secondary level students.

Table 2: Final Selection of Sample from Modern and Indigenous Schools

Types of school		Total Number of Students		
		Male	Female	Total
Modern schools	U.P. Board schools	72	71	143
	CBSE schools	78	79	157

Indigenous schools	Gurukula	70	60	130
	Madrassa	80	90	170
TOTAL		300	300	600

Research method of the study:

Descriptive survey method of research was used in this study.

Tool of the study:

Spiritual Intelligence Scale (self-constructed) by researcher has been employed in this study.

Table 3: Item-wise Distribution of Preliminary Draft of SIS

S.N.	Dimensions	Number of Items
1.	Knowledge of God	10
2.	Self-Awareness	10
3	Spiritual-Actualization	08
4	Kindness	08
5	Altruism	08
6	Social-Maturity	08
7	Meditation ,Yoga & Soul/Sprit	08
	Total	60

After deciding the dimensions of the Spiritual Intelligence Scale, the researcher prepared a layout of the scale that was 5 point rating scale. Students were with five options to give opinion namely strongly agree, agree, undecided, disagree and strongly disagree.

Reliability of SIS

Test-retest reliability of the tool was established by the researcher in the present study. Hundred Secondary level students were taken for calculating the reliability of the tool. The Spiritual Intelligence Scale was administered on secondary level students after one month later same test was again administered on the same sample. The calculated coefficient correlation between the scores of both administered tests was found to be **0.82**.

Validity of SIS

The final Spiritual Intelligence Scale was given to ten educationalists. Educationalists examined the content of each item and were found to agree with each

other to great extent. Thus, the face validity of the SIS was established by discussing it with educationalists. The content validity of the Scale was established through *Lushes' Content Validity Index*. Thus, found a high *content validity* of **0.88**.

Scoring of SIS

All fifty statements were divided into 5 point rating scale i.e. strongly agrees, agree, undecided, disagree, strongly disagree. Five marks were for the response strongly agree, four marks for agree, three marks for undecided, two marks for disagree and one mark for strongly disagree of Spiritual Intelligence Scale. The statement on which more than one response is given or no response given was scored as 0.

Table 4: Scoring of Spiritual Intelligence Scale

S.N.	Rating scale	Scores
1.	Strongly agree	5
2.	Agree	4
3.	Undecided	3
4.	Disagree	2
5.	Strongly disagree	1

Final Spiritual Intelligence Scale

Table 5: Features of Spiritual Intelligence Scale

S.N.	Author	By Researcher
1.	Year of construction	2019
2.	Name of the tool	Spiritual Intelligence Scale
3.	Applicability	17+ age group
4.	Language	Hindi and English
5.	Time limit	No Time limit
6.	Items	50
7.	Reliability	Test-retest (0.82)
8.	Validity	Content Validity (0.88)

Statistical Techniques:

For determining nature of distribution of data, Numerical methods and Visual methods were employed for checking the normality of Spiritual Intelligence Scale scores. The

researcher used descriptive statistics as Skewness and Kurtosis and Shapiro-Wilk as normality test.

Data Analysis and Interpretation:

Analysis and interpretation of data was carried out in two phase's viz. determining the distribution of Spiritual Intelligence Scale scores and comparison of Spiritual Intelligence Scale scores of Modern and Indigenous school students.

Table 6: Skewness and Kurtosis Value of Variable

Variable	Skewness			Kurtosis		
	Statistics (s)	SE	Sig (S/SE)	Statistics (S)	SE	Sig (S/SE)
Spiritual Intelligence	0.268	0.260	1.03	0.216	0.427	0.50

Table 6 shows that calculated value of Skewness & Kurtosis for Spiritual Intelligence Scale. This value is less than ± 1.96 . Thus, the distribution of data fulfills the assumption of normality. Further, from the column values obtained, it can be observed that the distribution of Spiritual Intelligence Scale (Skewness=1.03) was slightly positively skewed. This slight deviation in Skewness indicates that scores of Spiritual Intelligence Scale were more concentrated towards the lower side of the scale. The values of Kurtosis indicates that the distribution of Spiritual Intelligence Scale were Leptokurtic as their values of statistics are lesser than 0.263. Thus, the distribution of scores of Spiritual Intelligence Scale can be considered as normal.

Table 7: Shapiro-Wilk Test for Assessing the Normality of Spiritual Intelligence Scale

Variables	Shapiro-Wilk (Stats.)	Sig. (p-value)
Spiritual Intelligence	0.985	0.330

It can be visualized from the table 7 that the value of Shapiro-Wilk statistics for Spiritual Intelligence was found to be 0.985. Variables of study have corresponding significant value (p-value) as 0.330 which was greater than the standard value 0.01. Therefore, the

data are normally distributed and the distribution of scores of variable fulfilled the criteria of normality. Thus, the distribution of scores can be considered as normal on the basis of Skewness, Kurtosis and Shapiro-Wilk test.

Since, the distribution of variable of study was normal therefore, Parametric Statistics were executed for the analysis of the study.

Table 8: Mean, S.D and CR-value of the Scores Obtained on Spiritual Intelligence Scale of Modern and Indigenous School Students

Variable	Schools	N	M	S.D	CR-value	Level of significance
Spiritual Intelligence	Modern school	300	177.5	14.68	4.03	Significance at 0.01 level
	Indigenous school	300	182.3	14.64		

Table 8 depicts that mean score (177.5) of Modern school students was comparatively less than mean score (182.3) of Indigenous school students. Obtained CR-value (4.03) was greater than 2.58 i.e., table value at 0.01 level of significance. Hence, the null hypothesis i.e., there exists no significant difference between the Spiritual Intelligence of secondary level students studying in Modern and Indigenous schools was rejected at 0.01 level of significance. Therefore, there exists a significant difference between the Spiritual Intelligence of Modern and Indigenous school students. Indigenous school students were found to have high Spiritual Intelligence in comparison to students studying in Modern school students. This significance difference in spiritual intelligence can be attributed to a difference in curriculum and the teaching methods which relies on real life situations etc.

Conclusion:

This study played an important role in Spiritual Intelligence which teachers and parents can jointly carry out efforts to enhance it. Thus, Spiritual Intelligence can be enhanced by adopted teaching methods, conducting general life-skill programs, delivered content, proper school environment and conduct co-curricular activities, etc. Spiritual Intelligence should be given attention by teachers, family members, and administrators for providing them a proper atmosphere to increase student's potential related to Spiritual Intelligence so that they can succeed in their life and face various challenges of life.

Significance of the study:

In the families we can see that sometimes children who are being punished by their guardians react very frequently and they have become soon get angry, impatient, suffer from depressions etc. when often result in to commit suicide.

Unfortunately, there is no satisfaction in our life because we are always remaining in the condition of demand something. Today our need have been grown to the extent limit. This thing makes us peace less and we always try to get some more happiness through materialistic things. But this is our doubt because real happiness cannot be attained by the worldly things. Thus, spiritual intelligence can play a major role to overcome their problems S.Q can make students to improve mental balance and help them to understand the meaning & value of life.

For the development of students it is necessary to develop an ability & intelligence to cope with mental peace & this can only be done by managing their emotions. S.Q. can play a major role is managing social adjustments. S.I. can help adolescents to look with in to know, to understand and the nature of the self and its requirement. S.I. enhances their total outlook. It makes students positive and careful. Positive thinking makes one physically and mentally better equipped to manage mental balance.

For the proper development of an individual as well as nation, it is necessary to give proper direction, which can be given by schools & parents also. But schools are more important than parents as they can provide more opportunities for the development of S.I. So the researcher is of the view that if the study would be positive, this would help the parents, society as well as for the development of nation also. Teachers would get feedback by the study & help students to provide many enhancement programs. They can organize such activities in schools, which can develop S.I. in students. The study would be helpful for curriculum planners, what curriculum & which activities should be provided to the students. So the students can develop their S.I.

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